

INTERACTIVE TEACHING METHODS

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Annotation: this article explores and explains through examples what interactive teaching methods are in pedagogical technologies that are currently being used in the educational system.

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A. Verbitsky believes that "active teaching" is understood as the transition from regulated, algorithmic, programmed forms and methods in the didactic process to developing, problematic, exploratory methods that stimulate cognitive activity and create a creative environment. M. Novik distinguishes the following aspects of active teaching: - that the student is active in a way that he does not want; - that the student's active is stationary throughout the lesson, not in an episodic character; - creativity in solving problems, a high level of emotionality; Interactive methods, organizers are used to increase the activity of students in the lesson. The use of interactive methods in the educational process is primarily intended not to give students ready-made knowledge, but to give them the skills to reflect, form a culture of communication with those around them, have an independent opinion and independently search for some necessary knowledge and find a solution to the problem. Nowadays, the number of innovative technologies, interactive Styles has increased a lot. We will analyze them by citing the methodology of use of certain pedagogical technologies that can be used in the exact sciences and subjects to be studied, which are common in educational institutions.

1) "dating" technology the purpose of technology: to introduce the participants of the educational team to each other, to create a sincere friendly attitude and creative atmosphere; to reveal the creative capabilities and personal qualities of students. Procedure for conducting training: at the beginning of training, the teacher divides the participants of the educational process into small groups. Each sub-group can include students born in one season of the year.

The teacher transfers groups to their places and gives them the following assignment:

- give characterizations to your birth season (in the form of artistic - musical, stage, humorous, etc.);
- familiarize yourself with the general character of those born in this season of the year, as well as with the general similarities and specific aspects of the group participants;
- talk about the activities of students in this At the end, the teacher addresses with the following questions:
- -What did the participants in the group learn about each other; - how did the state of getting used to each other change in the audience;
- -what questions and problems were solved;

- what qualities were the participants able to show during the lesson; - what conclusion did each person draw for himself;

2) "dating" technology when the teacher divides the students into small groups, each group is called "Let's get to know!" distributes hypothetical material of the following content in which the theme is written: Let's get to know!.

- Who are you and why are you gathered here?
- What unites you?
- What is the most valuable thing for you? - What helps you work?
- Who do you care about?
- Who do you cooperate with?
- What do you decide for yourself and what together?
- What are your strongest and weakest sides?.

Together, the members of the group prepare to answer questions in the distribution material, in the process of preparation they get to know each other.

3) the style "analysis of concepts" is the essence of the style. This technique is aimed at memorizing all the subjects of the educational subject or department mentioned by the students, independently giving their own comments to the concepts given by the teacher on any topic, thereby providing an opportunity to check and evaluate their knowledge and be able to evaluate all students in a short time by the teacher. The purpose of the style. Teach students to determine the degrees of mastery of the subject mentioned in the training and mastery of the basic concepts of the subject, to be able to freely describe their knowledge independently, to assess their level of knowledge, to work alone and in groups, to respect the opinion of their ranks, as well as to put their knowledge into one system.

Procedure for conducting training:

- divides students into groups; - students are introduced to the requirements and rules imposed on conducting training;
- dissemination materials are distributed to group members.
- students get acquainted with the concepts given in the dissemination material on the topic or new topic, individually;
- students write a footnote on the basis of their (or their own) knowledge (as they understand the concepts given) on the topic in the dissemination material (individually);
- the teacher reads the concepts given on the topic in the dissemination material and together with the team;
- each student (or student) determines the differences in the answers established by the correct answer, acquires the necessary understanding, checks themselves, evaluates, and also once again strengthens their knowledge.

4) technology "ZINAMA-ZINA" is a description of the technology. This training teaches students to think individually and in a small team on a topic that is or should be passed on, and to remember, to memorize acquired knowledge, to be able to summarize the accumulated thoughts and to express them in the form of writing, painting, drawing. This technology is conducted and presented in writing with students in a group, either alone or in groups. The purpose of the technology. Teaching students to think freely, independently and logically, to work as a team, to search, to form a theoretical and practical concept from them by summing up thoughts, to be able to influence the team with their opinion, to approve it, as well as to apply the knowledge acquired in commenting on the basic concepts of the subject. The

procedure for conducting the training: - the teacher divides students into small groups of 3-5 people, depending on the number of subjects (the number of groups is 4 or 5 maqul); - students are introduced to the purpose of the training and the order in which it is conducted. To each group, on the left side of the paper, sheets with a small topic inscription are distributed;

- the teacher gives the members of the group the task of getting acquainted with small topics written in the disseminated material and, using a felt
- tip pen what they know on the basis of this topic, to write down in a joint thought with the team on a blank sheet of paper and set a time;
- the members of the group together express a small topic In doing so, the group members will have to provide as complete information as possible on a small topic.
- once the handouts are filled, a person from the group's members makes a presentation. At the time of the presentation, the material prepared by the groups will definitely be attached to the auditorium (classroom) board logically tagma-tag (in the form of a dungeon);
- the teacher will comment on the materials prepared by the groups, evaluate them and complete the training.

5) "Carpenter" Technology description of the technology. This technology is aimed at teaching students to memorize the topics covered, logically think, independently correctly answer the questions posed and self-evaluate, and in a short time evaluate the knowledge acquired by the teacher of all students. The purpose of technology: to teach students to think logically in the course of the lesson, to be able to freely express their thoughts independently, to evaluate themselves, to work alone and in groups, to respect the opinion of others, to choose the necessary one from many thoughts.

The procedure for conducting the training:

- to divide students (depending on the circumstances) into groups;
- to familiarize the student (or student) with the requirements and rules for conducting the training;
- to distribute handouts to group members.
- tasks in distribution materials are performed independently by the members of the group;
- each group member writes a group number in the right corner of the distribution material he worked on, and in the left corner he draws any signs of himself;
- the distribution materials performed by the task are exchanged in the direction of "Carpenter's turnover" to other groups;
- materials given;
- materials studied and modified by teams are again exchanged intergroup in the direction mentioned above (this process is continued according to the number of groups);
- after the last exchange of materials, each group and each group member selects the materials they first completed (based on the group number and the marks they put);
- compares and analyzes the corrections of other group members;
- reads the tasks of the student given in the disseminated material and, together with the team, determines the correct answers;
- each student (or student) determines the differences in the answers determined by the correct answer, collects the desired score and self-evaluates.

Once students have determined their grades or scores, the student will collect the papers on which the task is completed and copy the grade (scores) into the group Journal.

6) "boomerang" technology (option 1) description of the technology. This technology aims to make students work with different literature, texts in the course of the lesson, outside the lesson, keep the material studied in mind, speak, be able to freely state their mind, have a lot of information in a short time and be able to evaluate all students by the teacher during the lesson. The purpose of the technology. Control and assessment of the extent to which the materials distributed during the educational process are mastered by students in a single and group state, and to what extent the texts in the disseminated materials are mastered through conversation and discussion and various questions. To provide an opportunity for each student (or student) to gain their own grade (or points) during the learning process. The procedure for conducting training.

This technology is carried out in several stages:

- students are divided into small groups;
- students are introduced to the purpose and order of the lesson (training);
- texts on the topic are distributed to students for independent study;
- the texts given are independently studied by students individually;
- a new group is formed from each group of members;
- each of the members of the new group exchanges information within the group with independently studied texts, respectively, that is, they speak to each other, achieve text assimilation;
- internal control within the group;
- members of the new group return to their groups in the initial state;
- in the rest of the course, a "group accountant" is appointed in each group to assess student knowledge or calculate the points earned;
- in order to determine to what extent all texts are mastered by students, the teacher (or opposite group) addresses students with questions, conducts an oral survey;
- one question is drawn up by each group member, linking the content of the text in the group to life;
- through questions prepared by groups, a question-answer is organized ("group accountants" calculate points on the answers given);
- the sum of the total points accumulated by the group members is determined;
- the total points earned by the groups are evenly distributed among the group members.

7) "boomerang" technology this technology is aimed at studying the educational material in a deep and holistic state during one session, creative understanding, free possession. It is intended to explore subjects with different content and character (problematic, controversial, with different content), and can be done in oral and written forms of work. Technology provides the opportunity for each participant to complete different tasks during the training, take turns in the role of a student (or student) or teacher, and accumulate suitable points. "Boomerang" technology provides students with the opportunity to think critically, form logic in them, and also develops skills to state their memory, ideas, thoughts, arguments in written and oral forms.

This style is educational in addition to teaching students:

- skill of working with a team;

- attitude;
- kindness;
- skillfulness;
- skillfulness;
- respect for the opinion of others;
- activity;
- creative approach to work;
- heat up the effectiveness of their activities;
- provides the opportunity to form a number of qualities, such as self-assessment.

8) "3x4" technology description of the technology. This training teaches students to solve a specific problem (or a topic) in private (or as a small team), find a solution, Choose the right one from many thoughts, generalize selected thoughts and form a clear understanding of the problem (or topic) posed on their basis, as well as be able to approve their thoughts. This technology is conducted in writing with students, first alone and then dividing them into subgroups.

➤ The purpose of technology: to teach students to think freely, independently and logically;

➤ to work as a team, to search; to concentrate thoughts, to draw theoretical and practical understanding from them; to transfer their opinion to the team, to approve it;

➤ to be able to apply the knowledge acquired from the topics covered in solving the problem posed and giving a general understanding Procedure for conducting training:

➤ the teacher divides students into small groups of 3-5 people, depending on the total number of students;

➤ the teacher introduces students to the purpose and order of transfer of training and distributes sheets with an inscription on the top of the paper to each small group;

➤ the teacher promotes the fact that members of the small group can continue with;

➤ the band members continue to record together the idea given in the distribution material;

➤ when the task is completed, the band members get up and change places Clockwise;

➤ the band members who come to the new location get acquainted with the thoughts in the distribution material left there and write down their thoughts on it again from the new three;

➤ the band members change places again;

➤ small groups returning to their place carefully read all the thoughts collected in the disseminated material and bring them to a single holistic definition or rule state, summarizing them;

➤ one of the members of the group presents the author's definitions or rules of each subgroup;

the teacher evaluates them, commenting on the definitions or rules given by small groups, and then completes the.

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